

Direct-Patterning ZnO Deposition by Atomic-Layer Additive Manufacturing Using a Safe and Economical Precursor

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Area-selective atomic layer deposition (AS-ALD) is a bottom-up nanofabrication method delivering single atoms from a molecular precursor. AS-ALD enables self-aligned fabrication and outperforms lithography in terms of cost, resistance, and equipment prerequisites, but it requires pre-patterned substrates and is limited by insufficient selectivity and finite choice of substrates. These challenges are circumvented by direct patterning with atomic-layer additive manufacturing (ALAM) — a transfer of 3D-printing principles to atomic-layer manufacturing where a precursor supply nozzle enables direct patterning instead of blanket coating. The reduced precursor vapor consumption in ALAM as compared with ALD calls for the use of less volatile precursors by replacing diethylzinc used traditionally in ALD with bis(dimethylaminopropyl)zinc, Zn(DMP)₂. The behavior of this novel ZnO ALAM process follows that of the corresponding ALD in terms of deposit quality and growth characteristics. The temperature window for self-limiting growth of stoichiometric, crystalline material is 200–250 °C. The growth rates are 0.9 Å per cycle in ALD (determined by spectroscopic ellipsometry) and 1.1 Å per pass in ALAM (imaging ellipsometry). The preferential crystal orientation increases with temperature, while energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopic and XPS show that only intermediate temperatures deliver stoichiometric ZnO. A functional thin-film transistor is created from an ALAM-deposited ZnO line and characterized.

However, generating patterns still relies on lithographic processing. When the chemical control of ALD is exploited to deposit specifically on certain surface terminations at the exclusion of others, one obtains area-selective atomic layer deposition (AS-ALD), or just area-selective deposition (ASD).^[2] ASD enables self-aligned fabrication without dedicated lithographic steps. However, the need for pre-patterned substrates is inherent to ASD and still requires the use of lithography in preliminary processing. Further limitations of ASD include the generation of defects outside of the desired growth area and the limited selection of adequate substrate materials. To overcome these limitations, we have recently invented atomic-layer additive manufacturing (ALAM): a direct-patterning atomic layer 3D-printing method based on a microfluidic nozzle design that can deposit arbitrary patterns of materials with atomic precision using the underlying chemical principles of ALD.^[3] With respect to methods reliant on lithography, ALAM increases flexibility and reduces manufacturing cost and time, while still delivering atomic resolution (on

the vertical axis). Defining the lateral resolution of ALAM is an exercise in several steps. First, the routine line width obtained with our current microfluidic precursor delivery nozzle is 400 μm. However, this value depends on the geometry of the nozzle and we have already demonstrated that lines of 100 and 50 μm width are possible with more advanced nozzle designs.

1. Introduction

Atomic layer deposition (ALD) allows for the blanket deposition of thin coatings using molecular surface control.^[1] Essentially, it is a bottom-up nanofabrication method that places individual atoms as the building blocks of the solid being grown.

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DOI: 10.1002/smll.202301774

With adequate nozzles and controls, line widths in the low micron range will be possible in the near future. Additionally, the actual resolution is better than the linewidth and is defined by the accuracy and reproducibility of the sample motion stage, which is in the sub-micron regime. Thus, a partial overlap of two micron-wide lines can be set to result in a feature on the sub-micron range.

The deposition chemistry of ALAM is similar to conventional ALD and all the commercially available gaseous precursors used in ALD are compatible with ALAM. However, the extremely low areas being coated translate into low gas and precursor vapor flow rates, and therefore, much-reduced precursor consumption. In fact, we have observed that precursors with high vapor pressure and high reactivity, which are typically the most desired ones in the ALD community (such as trimethylaluminum and diethylzinc), tend to cause issues in ALAM. Conversely, the minimized precursor consumption of ALAM allows us to explore new reactions with precursors which are not relevant in industrial-scale ALD owing to more elaborate synthetic procedures and cost but still exhibit exploitable vapor pressure and adjusted reactivity. As an example, we establish in this paper a novel atomic-layer reaction for the deposition of ZnO in ALD and ALAM using Zn(DMP)₂ (DMP = dimethylaminopropyl) as the zinc precursor (in combination with water) instead of the classic diethylzinc (ZnEt₂, DEZ).^[4] The DMP ligand stabilizes the zinc central atom through chelation via the terminal dimethylamino functionality, rendering the precursor less reactive and therefore much safer to handle since the compound is no longer pyrophoric. The comparably large molecular mass of Zn(DMP)₂ also contributes to its lesser volatility, which further increases its safety but requires heating of the precursor canister for efficient gas phase transport (1 Torr of vapor pressure delivered at ≈75 °C). It has been used so far as a reducing agent for the ALD of metallic Co, in a plasma-enhanced process, and in the deposition of zinc oxide, but not in a thermal reaction for the ALD of ZnO.^[4–6]

This study will establish the use of Zn(DMP)₂ for the ALD of ZnO, then transfer the deposition chemistry to ALAM. In ALAM, lines and patterns of ZnO are continuous, display sharp edges, and offer residual-free surfaces. The solid is crystalline and the crystallites can be either isotropically or preferentially oriented depending on the chosen growth conditions and the targeted application. Finally, we demonstrate the technological potential of ZnO ALAM direct patterning by fabricating metal oxide field effect transistors and characterizing the device performance. This application also highlights the advantage of ALAM as a prototyping strategy, since a large number of ZnO FET channels can be printed with various geometric parameters (length and thickness) in a single processing step and tested subsequently.

Taken together, these results highlight how ALAM can advantageously use precursors that exhibit lower vapor pressure and reactivity than typically employed for ALD, thereby reducing the consumption of materials, minimizing waste, and enhancing chemical safety. They also demonstrate how simple patterns can be generated directly, in the absence of lithographic processing, allowing for rapid prototyping of functional devices.

2. Results and Discussion

The classic ZnO ALD reaction using ZnEt₂ and water as the precursors yield a growth rate in slight excess of 1 Å per cycle with self-limiting growth at substrate temperatures between 105 and 165 °C.^[7] When combined with water in a regular hot-wall ALD reactor, Zn(DMP)₂ also yields films at 150 °C. The process optimization is carried out on Si with native oxide. A saturation study using various pulse durations of the Zn(DMP)₂ maintained at 70 °C delivers the type of curve expected of a self-limiting surface chemistry, which defines the ALD growth mode (blue curve in Figure 1a displaying film thicknesses determined by spectroscopic ellipsometry). The growth rate, however, seems to saturate rather slowly, suggesting the use of shorter but repeated pulses as a more efficient delivery method. Such double pulses indeed yield a faster approach to the saturated growth per cycle (GPC) of 1.1 Å (red curve in Figure 1a). Therefore, in the following, we will apply this double-pulse method for ALD growth. Using the optimized pulse duration, a variation of the number of cycles performed results in a linear increase of the film thickness measured by ellipsometry (Figure 1b).

The morphology of these films after 500 cycles, presented on the left of Figure 2, exhibits a roughness that suggests crystallinity both in scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and atomic force microscopy (AFM). Films grown at more elevated temperatures (200 and 250 °C) look similar on both length scales, as well (Figure 2). Over the broad range of temperatures, the deposits are highly homogeneous and free of pinholes and particles.

X-ray diffraction performed in grazing incidence (GI-XRD) on the same samples obtained after 500 cycles confirms the crystalline quality of all films (Figure 3). In all cases, the various reflexes can be indexed to the hexagonal phase of ZnO.

The intensity ratios between the reflexes, however, vary significantly with the deposition temperature. Starting from near isotropy at 150 °C, the system evolves to an increasingly marked preferential orientation along the (001) direction. This direction is of particular importance for applications related to the piezo-

Figure 1. ALD growth of ZnO from Zn(DMP)₂ + H₂O at 150 °C. a) Demonstration of self-limiting surface chemistry by variation of pulse durations. Double pulsing (red) allows one to reach saturation faster. b) Linearity of growth. All thicknesses are determined by spectroscopic ellipsometry. The uncertainties determined by repeating at least four individual measurements at each thickness go from 1 nm at 20 nm film thickness (5% relative uncertainty) to 2 nm at 80 nm thickness (2.5% relative uncertainty).

Figure 2. Microscopic characterization of ALD ZnO films deposited at three different temperatures on Si/SiO₂: a) 150 °C, b) 200 °C, c) 250 °C. Top, scanning electron microscopy; second line, atomic force microscopy (5 × 5 μm²).

electric properties of ZnO, therefore a test performed at 250 °C delivers an optimized (001)-oriented material (Figure 3c).

However, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopic (EDX) microanalysis showed a notable dependency of the film composition and Zn to O ratio on the deposition temperature. The thin films grown at 200 and 250 °C offer a nearly perfect 1:1 ratio between the elements Zn and O (specifically, 50:50 at 200 °C and 52:48 at 250 °C) but the stoichiometry deviates beyond those boundaries. At 150 °C, the Zn: O ratio is 30:70, which could very well correspond to a highly hydrated ZnO film. At 295 °C, the ratio is inverted to Zn: O 59:41, which in turn indicates a highly

defective layer not ideal for the targeted transistor application. In this conventional ALD process, 295 °C marks the temperature at which non-ideal film growth takes place, likely owing to partial thermal decomposition of the Zn(DMP)₂ precursor.

Transferring the optimized ALD conditions to ALAM, 200 °C was chosen as the initial deposition temperature. Figure 4 exhibits simple lines obtained by ALAM. A scanning electron micrograph of three parallel lines (Figure 4a) shows that the edges are sharp and no uncontrolled deposition occurs beyond the desired pattern area. This is in stark contrast to the observations made when attempting to use DEZ as an ALAM precursor:

Figure 3. X-ray diffractograms recorded in grazing incidence for ALD films of ZnO deposited at 150 °C (a), 200 °C (b), and 250 °C (c) on Si/SiO₂. The insets represent the respective energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) microanalyses. The standard deviations on EDX data, obtained by repeating at least three measurements each on three samples of different thicknesses (150, 500, and 800 cycles) at each temperature (minimum 9 individual measurements at each temperature), are 10% at 150 °C, 1% at 200 °C, and 5% at 250 °C.

Figure 4. ZnO lines printed by ALAM on Si/SiO₂. a) Scanning electron micrograph of three lines with 800, 600, and 400 passes (from left to right). b) Optical micrograph of six lines with 50 to 800 passes as labeled, preceded by a line used to purge the system during 200 passes.

Our earlier results employing DEZ as the Zn precursor indicate clearly how non-ideal deposition behaves in an ALAM setup, with significant amounts of white powdery or rough material deposited within several millimeters of the actual deposition lines. With Zn(DMP)₂ as the precursor, instead, repeating depositions with increasing numbers of cycles *N* results in lines of scalable thicknesses which by eye or in optical microscopy have various colors caused by interference effects (Figure 4b).

With which fidelity does the transfer from ALD to ALAM occur? **Figure 5** compares several characteristics of growth in these two distinct modes. The thicknesses for ALAM-grown films are very similar to those obtained from classic ALD with increasing cycles numbers and obtained at various temperatures (as determined by spectroscopic ellipsometry in Figure 5a) are very similar to those obtained in ALAM (with an additional temperature value, as determined by imaging ellipsometry, and confirmed by atomic force microscopy, in Figure 5b). Not only the slopes of the individual curves are very similar, but also the shape of the growth rate dependence on temperature is identical (Figure 5c). The measured ALAM growth rate is systematically higher than in ALD mode by 10% to 20%. This difference could possibly result from the distinct thickness measurement methods used, although we were careful to use the optical parameters determined by spectroscopic ellipsometry for the imaging ellipsometry fitting procedure. Minute differences in the density of the deposited material could potentially skew the results. The roughness, which could be another source of error, is very similar in both cases (Figure 2 and Figure 7 below). However, the difference could be real, as well. In fact, in academic research, the inhomogeneity of film thickness observed for large samples over the size of the ALD chamber is often on the order of 10%. Therefore, we would refrain for over-interpreting the difference between ALAM and ALD growth rates at this point.

In the broader context, these results highlight the possibility of transferring thin film forming chemistry from conventional ALD to ALAM. Apart from a small shift which may be caused by the distinct thickness determination methods, the parallelism of the windows of constant growth rate proves

Figure 5. Comparison of growth characteristics in ALD and ALAM. a) Film thickness as a function of temperature and applied number of cycles obtained in ALD (thicknesses determined by spectroscopic ellipsometry) at three different temperatures as noted. b) Similar dataset (thicknesses determined by imaging ellipsometry, three wavelengths) for ALAM. c) Variation of the growth rate (thickness growth per cycle or per pass) with temperature as determined for ALD (black) and ALAM (red): the window over which the growth rate remains constant is identical in both cases. Relative uncertainties on the thickness and GPC values are on the order of 5% at 20 nm and 2% at 130 nm (see Figure 1 for spectroscopic ellipsometry, similar approach, and similar results for imaging ellipsometry).

how self-limiting surface chemistry controls deposition and growth in both ALD and ALAM. Consequently, the desired “ALD window” in which the reproducible growth of quality thin films is ensured was demonstrated in both processes: While depositions in the temperature range between 150 and 200 °C are found to yield low growth rates due to insufficient precursor reactivity; nearly temperature-independent film growth is observed between 200 and 250 °C, with GPCs of ≈0.9 Å (ALD) and 1.1 Å (ALAM). Above 250 °C, precursor decomposition leads to a notably increased GPC accompanied by a mismatch in film composition (oxygen deficiency).^[2]

We note that even very thin lines (20, 50, 80, and 100 cycles, corresponding to ≈ 2, 5, 9, and 11 nm thickness) are achievable by ALAM and feature characteristics that are in line with those presented here (Figure S1, Supporting Information).

Further insight is provided by imaging ellipsometry thickness maps, **Figure 6** right. Again, a straight line with sharp edges is observed in Figure 6 middle. No material is found beyond the confines of the line. The thickness is not perfectly constant along the length of the line as quantified in a profile

Figure 6. Line profile and line thickness maps measured by imaging ellipsometry. a) Height profile of a ZnO line ALAM-printed with 250 passes (200 °C), along its long axis. b) ZnO thickness map of the same line (400 μm width). c) ZnO thickness map of five lines featuring increasing numbers of passes.

(Figure 6 left), but this is a known effect caused at the extremity of ALAM lines by the concentric arrangement of the precursor delivery lines (which causes the extremity of the line to experience only one ALD cycle per back-and-forth motion instead of two ALD cycles.^[3] Along the perpendicular axis, the box shape of the profile with a horizontal plateau and sharp edges is yet another confirmation of the self-limited nature of our process.

The material quality is very similar to that demonstrated above in ALD mode. **Figure 7** summarizes our material characterization in a manner that parallels what we show above for ALD. In SEM and AFM, the roughness values and sizes of individual crystallites are in the same range and follow a similar pattern. The crystallinity is also pronounced for all investigated samples and the preferential orientation is tunable based on the

Figure 7. Characterization of ALAM-deposited ZnO material. Top, scanning electron micrographs (scale bar, 100 nm); center, atomic force micrographs (5 × 5 μm²); lower line, X-ray diffractograms, and EDX analyses (bar graphs below). The four columns represent results obtained with deposition at 150 °C (a), 200 °C (b), 250 °C (c), and 295 °C (d). The standard deviations on EDX data, obtained by repeating at least three measurements each on five samples of different thicknesses (200, 300, 400, 500, and 1000 cycles) at each temperature (minimum 15 individual measurements at each temperature), are 3% at 150 °C, 5% at 200 °C, 4% at 250 °C, and 7% at 295 °C.

Figure 8. Representative XPS core level spectra recorded for as-introduced ZnO lines grown at 200 and 250 °C. a) Zn 2p core levels with doublet fit for the $2p_{3/2}$ and $2p_{1/2}$ spin-orbital components. b) Zn $L_3M_{4.5}M_{4.5}$ Auger feature recording with contributor species assignment. c) O 1s core levels with fits for attendant oxygen species.

deposition temperature chosen. Even the composition behaves in a manner that follows the observations made in ALD, with the EDX Zn: O ratio going from substoichiometric at 150 °C (40:60) to stoichiometric within the ALD window (49:51 at 200 °C; 47:53 at 250 °C) and back to substoichiometric beyond it (42:58 at 295 °C).

Further detail is provided by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, survey spectrum shown as Figure S2, Supporting Information). Within the Zn 2p core level region, a Zn 2p spin-orbit doublet with well-separated, symmetrically shaped peaks is observed as expected (Figure 8a: Zn $2p_{3/2}$ component at 1021.8 eV / 200 °C growth, 1021.7 eV / 250 °C; Zn $2p_{1/2}$ at 1044.9 and 1044.8 eV, respectively). These values and the spin separation of $\Delta = 23.1$ eV were in good agreement with the literature on ZnO that reported these components to appear at 1021.5–1022.1 eV and 1044.5–1045.2 eV.^[8–10] The narrow full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the Zn $2p_{3/2}$ spin component at 1.8 eV (200 °C) and 1.7 eV (250 °C) matches the FWHM reported between 1.7 and 1.9 eV for pure ZnO and excludes the presence of an underlying contribution from reduced, metallic Zn. While these results are indicative of ZnO, it is known that the Zn 2p core level feature exhibits little sensitivity toward altered chemical environments of Zn-bonded O. A more sensitive handle is provided by the Zn Auger features.^[11,12] Following a procedure by Xing and co-workers, the Zn $L_3M_{4.5}M_{4.5}$ Auger feature located ≈ 500 eV (Al $K\alpha$ photon radiation) was subjected to further analysis (Figure 8b).^[13] For both samples, the Auger feature comprises two components exhibiting binding energies of 498.0 and 494.8 eV. The higher binding energy contribution can be ascribed to fully oxygen-coordinated Zn^{2+} ions in the hexagonal wurtzite structure arrangement, while the lower binding energy contribution is associated with oxygen-deficient,

incompletely coordinated Zn^{2+} ions often referred to as interstitial Zn ions.^[11,13] Based on the integral shares, the ZnO line grown at 200 °C seems to exhibit a slightly higher portion of fully coordinated Zn^{2+} species (72.2%) compared to the line grown at 250 °C (68.5%). This observation corroborates the data of Figure 7 to define 200 °C as the deposition temperature that yields the best-quality material.

Even more notable differences between the two samples become apparent from the assessment of the O 1s core level region shown in Figure 8c. Here, the 200 °C deposit demonstrates an overall signal shape dominated by two contributions, while the 250 °C ZnO line exhibits a single peak with an asymmetric shape. Within both signals, however, the same three contributors are identified based on the literature: lattice oxygen fully integrated into the wurtzite type structure (529.9–530.2 eV), chemisorbed oxygen occupying vacancies (530.7–531.2 eV), and oxygen present in the form of hydroxyls (532.1–532.4 eV).^[14–18] The data show how the deposition temperature impacts the chemical identity of oxygen in our ZnO material. At 200 °C, lattice oxygen at 530.1 eV contributes 33%, oxygen in vacancies at 531.0 eV $\approx 13\%$, and hydroxyls at 532.2 eV represent with 54% of the majority of oxygen. For the 250 °C ZnO line, the lattice oxygen and oxygen vacancy species have nearly equal integral shares with 43% and 42%, respectively. Only 14% of hydroxides are found at this elevated temperature. In addition to this, the Zn:O surface ratios determined for both samples amount to 48:52 for the line grown at 200 °C and 54:46 at 250 °C. Based on the normalized peak area counts for the Zn 2p and O 1s core level regions, it is reasonable to assume an experimental uncertainty on the Zn: O ratios of $\pm 6\%$. Thus, the XPS results are again in essentially perfect agreement with the EDX values, confirming the 200 °C growth conditions as

Figure 9. Characterization of a transistor based on an ALAM-printed ZnO line (250 °C). a) Transfer curves of a device with 250 μm source-drain distance at $V_D = 15$ V. One observes the typical feature $I_D \gg I_G$ (black and grey curves). b) Output curves of the same device exhibiting signs of saturation. c) Optical micrograph of a device including the two metal electrodes (yellow lines) separated by 100 μm and the ALAM-printed ZnO line underneath them (green/pink). The silicon wafer with thermally grown SiO_2 (100 nm) serves as the gate electrode with the corresponding gate dielectric layer (black background).

optimal. The two methods differ significantly in a single aspect: the Zn:O ratio for the 250 °C deposit implies a small oxygen deficiency in the surface-near region of ZnO (XPS) that is in contrast with the oxygen excess indicated by EDX for the bulk of the solid. These observations may originate from the onset of Zn precursor decomposition during the line growth itself.

The numbers extracted from XPS analyses should not be taken as absolute. However, they confirm the overall high material quality and the potential differences in chemical composition caused by different deposition conditions. These may therefore have a profound influence on the electrical characteristics of the material. To investigate the electrical transport performance of our ZnO lines, let us now move to the characterization of model thin film transistor (TFT) devices based on an n-type channel layer consisting of 100 nm thick ZnO.

The TFT devices were fabricated by ALAM of ZnO as the semiconductor with top-contacted source and drain electrodes generated by a shadow mask on a Si / SiO_2 (100 nm thermal oxide) substrate serving as the gate electrode and dielectric, respectively. All TFTs exhibit the typical n-type characteristics, and a representative dataset based on ZnO deposited at 250 °C (250 μm length) is shown in **Figure 9**. Under positive gate voltage, the output characteristic of the device shows signs of saturation of the drain current at the high source-drain voltage (Figure 9b). The current reaches 60 nA under $V_D = 15$ V and $V_G = 35$ V (Figure 9a). The transfer curve of Figure 9a yields a mobility of $0.04 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and a current on/off ratio of 6000.

3. Conclusion

This study establishes a novel atomic layer deposition reaction for the accurate deposition of ZnO using a much safer Zn precursor than traditionally used in ALD. Its reactions are well behaved for blanket coating in ALD mode, and they are successfully transferred to ALAM. The material is of high quality as characterized in terms of stoichiometry and crystallinity and is optimal for deposition temperatures near 200 °C. ALAM-printed ZnO lines provide n-type semiconductor channels in functional thin-film transistors.

These results are significant in several different respects:

- First, ALAM yields patterns of lines or geometric areas directly without the need for lithographic processing in the building of functional devices. It thereby improves the speed and decreases costs for device prototyping. Large numbers of lines differing in their thickness, length, and even deposition temperature, can be printed on the same substrate in a single processing step, and subsequently characterized. Furthermore, direct ALAM pattern printing is economical for material as it circumvents the need for the removal of large areas of blanket-deposited material as required in lithographic processing. Finally, the fact that expensive lithographic equipment is not necessary renders the prototyping of devices accessible to a broader variety of research and development actors.
- Second, the deposition procedure itself minimizes the consumption of volatile precursors. In contrast to classical ALD, where the most commonly used, most successful precursors feature high vapor pressure and high reactivity, ALAM can exploit much lower vapor pressures by delivering them in a highly localized manner, minimizing waste. A back-of-the-envelope calculation based on typical precursor vapor pressures, precursor container volumes, and flow rates yields a consumption on the order of $50 \text{ nmol cycle}^{-1}$ in ALAM and $500 \mu\text{mol cycle}^{-1}$ in ALD — a difference by four orders of magnitude (in line with our qualitative experimental observations of vacuum line traps)!
- Third, the lower vapor pressure and lower reactivity needed short-circuits the otherwise necessary use of pyrophoric compounds in large amounts. This renders ALAM accessible to use in less specialized environments and by less highly trained users.
- Finally, this paper establishes the ease of transfer of ALD chemistry to ALAM. Our systematic comparison of deposition conditions and material characteristics obtained with both techniques demonstrates the almost absolute identical behavior. Composition, crystallinity, growth per cycle, and the deposition window all are identical in both cases. The major change in the transfer matrix is the lower partial pressure of precursor required in ALAM (with respect to ALD) and of course the lower carrier gas flow rates.

ZnO is a material of interest for its own sake in microelectronics, photovoltaics, sensors, and more, but the results presented here demonstrate the usefulness of ALAM and its advantages with respect to ALD in general. Sustainable manufacturing of miniaturized devices relies among other aspects on the minimization of precursor consumption and waste material removal, as well as on the exclusion of hazardous procedures. ALAM provides all these characteristics, and more: It reduces the number of processing steps required for the generation of devices and prototypes, accelerates turnover, and thereby, it also renders the economics aspect much more attractive.

4. Experimental Section

The film growth during thermal ALD of ZnO on the Si(100)/SiO₂ starting surfaces was studied in a custom-designed hot-wall ALD reactor by ModularFlow. The precursor vapors used in the ALD process were dosed using pneumatic valves working with 5 ms precision. The precursor bottle holding Zn(DMP)₂ was heated to 70 °C, and in the standard recipe the vapors were drawn using two pulses of 60 ms duration separated by 20 s. Water was maintained at room temperature and its vapor drawn with a single 20-ms long pulse. The substrate temperature was 200 °C in the standard recipe. Parameter variations deviating from these standard values are described in the Results Section.

In ALAM, a miniaturized gas delivery nozzle separated flows of precursors A and B vapors in space and moved over the substrate's surface based on principles described in a published paper.^[3] The temperatures for Zn precursor, water, and substrate were 55 °C, room temperature, and 200 °C, respectively. The stage velocity was set to 12 cm s⁻¹ and the carrier gas flow rate to 18 and 25 sccm through the two precursor bottles.

The thickness of blanket films on silicon wafers was measured by spectroscopic ellipsometry on a SENPro from SENTECH Instruments GmbH. The measurements were carried out at an angle of 70° and on a spectral range of 370–1050 nm. The film thicknesses were fitted with a model consisting of air/ZnO/SiO₂/Si stacks. Data analysis was performed with the software SpectraRay 3.

Grazing-incidence X-ray diffraction (GI-XRD) was performed using a D8 DISCOVER X-ray diffractometer (Bruker Corporation) with a Cu K α source (20 kV) under an incident angle of 0.5°. The Crystallographic Open Database was used to assign the diffraction pattern of crystalline ZnO.

For the SEM and EDX measurements, a JSM-F thermal field-emission scanning electron microscope (JEOL GmbH) with an acceleration voltage of 10 kV and a secondary electron detector was used. Images were analyzed with a self-developed protocol called ImageJ21 and Cell-pose22 software.^[1] AFM was performed with an OTESPA (–R3) tip by Atomic force Microscope Veeco NanoMan VS. Spring constant \approx 12 N m⁻¹, resonance $f \approx$ 300 kHz, tip radius \approx 7 nm, and Scan size 5 μ m.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) studies were carried out on a PHI 5000 VersaProbe II instrument utilizing Al K α photon radiation (1486.6 eV). Selected ZnO 3D-printed lines with a width larger than 100 μ m and grown at 200 and 250 °C were analyzed by a combination of survey scans and core level scans. Hereby, the pass energies were adjusted to 187.5 and 23.5 eV, respectively. All binding energies of Zn 2p, C 1s, O 1s, and N 1s core levels and Zn L3M4.5M4.5 Auger features were referenced to the signal of adventitious carbon at 284.8 eV. The analysis chamber pressure was maintained at $<10^{-7}$ mbar. Recordings were taken and analyzed in terms of chemical species and composition solely for the as-introduced surface to avoid preferential oxygen removal by Ar⁺ sputtering.^[19,20] The deconvolution analysis was completed with a Shirley background processing and Gaussian functions using the software UniFit 2017. The Zn L3M4.5M4.5 Auger feature was analyzed based on a procedure described by Xing et al. based on background subtraction.^[13]

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the European Research Council with the ERC Proof of Concept grant “Atomic-layer additive manufacturing of solar cells” (ALAMS, grant agreement 101069310) and by the European Union's H2020 projects “The atomic-layer 3D plotter (Atoplot, grant agreement 950785) and ‘All-in-one machine for hybrid technologies enabling high value-added multi-scale integrated micro-optoelectronics’ (Mesomorph, grant agreement 958417). The authors at RUB thank the DFG-SFB-TR-87 (B-04) for supporting this work. B.Z. (201706060215) acknowledges the China Scholarship Council (CSC).

Open access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

additive manufacturing, atomic layer deposition, nanofabrication, sensors, zinc oxide

Received: February 28, 2023

Revised: March 31, 2023

Published online:

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